

Table S2. Correlation between physicochemical properties of cultivation substrate and nutritional properties of *Pleurotus ostreatus* mushroom.

Variable		Nutritional properties of <i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i> mushroom								
		Pearson correlation coefficient (r-value) and Significance (p-value)	Moisture content	Ash content	Crude protein	Crude fiber	Crude lipid	Carbohydrate	Metabolizable energy	Beta glucan
Physicochemical properties of cultivation substrate	Wet bulk density	r-value	.783*	0.649	-0.275	0.13	-0.585	0.123	0.173	-0.665
		p-value	0.013	0.058	0.473	0.739	0.098	0.752	0.655	0.051
	Particle density	r-value	0.224	.866**	-0.813**	0.103	-0.251	0.5	0.097	-.733*
		p-value	0.562	0.003	0.008	0.792	0.514	0.17	0.804	0.025
	Porosity	r-value	-.768*	0	-0.517	-0.114	0.492	0.44	-0.189	0.176
		p-value	0.016	1	0.154	0.77	0.179	0.236	0.627	0.65
	pH	r-value	-0.152	-0.293	0.463	0.282	0.136	-0.666	0.231	0.346
		p-value	0.696	0.445	0.209	0.462	0.728	0.05	0.551	0.361
	Moisture content	r-value	0.197	0.24	0.082	0.025	-0.165	-0.128	0.038	-0.275
		p-value	0.612	0.533	0.833	0.948	0.671	0.743	0.923	0.474
	Ash content	r-value	.718*	0.207	0.284	-0.228	-0.095	0.004	-0.176	-0.124
		p-value	0.029	0.594	0.459	0.554	0.809	0.991	0.651	0.751
	Volatile solids content	r-value	-.718*	-0.207	-0.284	0.228	0.095	-0.004	0.176	0.124
		p-value	0.029	0.594	0.459	0.554	0.809	0.991	0.651	0.752
	Nitrogen	r-value	0.563	0.259	0.168	0.036	-0.056	-0.179	0.062	-0.166
		p-value	0.115	0.5	0.665	0.928	0.886	0.645	0.875	0.669
	Phosphorus	r-value	0.458	0.084	0.467	-0.55	0.082	0.167	-0.474	0.005
		p-value	0.215	0.831	0.205	0.125	0.833	0.667	0.198	0.99
	Potassium	r-value	0.013	-0.494	.706*	-0.635	0.314	0.088	-0.633	.701*
		p-value	0.973	0.176	0.034	0.066	0.41	0.821	0.068	0.035
	Calcium	r-value	0.264	-0.072	0.459	-0.473	0.308	0.045	-0.377	-0.027
		p-value	0.493	0.853	0.214	0.198	0.42	0.908	0.318	0.945
	Magnesium	r-value	0.303	-0.121	0.568	-0.563	0.254	0.077	-0.476	0.105
		p-value	0.427	0.757	0.11	0.114	0.51	0.843	0.196	0.788
	Iron	r-value	0.258	-0.176	0.276	-0.252	-0.23	0.17	-0.237	0.335
		p-value	0.502	0.651	0.473	0.513	0.552	0.662	0.539	0.378
	Zinc	r-value	0.463	0.284	0.034	-0.167	-0.262	0.185	-0.253	0.229
		p-value	0.209	0.458	0.931	0.669	0.495	0.633	0.512	0.554
Carbon	r-value	-0.359	0.306	-0.575	0.07	0.085	0.303	-0.052	-0.016	
	p-value	0.343	0.423	0.105	0.857	0.827	0.429	0.895	0.967	
Lignin	r-value	0.02	0.606	-.901**	0.498	-0.263	0.216	0.471	-0.615	
	p-value	0.959	0.084	0.001	0.172	0.495	0.576	0.201	0.078	
Hemicellulose	r-value	-0.166	-0.301	0.048	-0.231	-0.016	0.297	-0.256	0.467	
	p-value	0.67	0.431	0.903	0.549	0.967	0.438	0.507	0.205	
Cellulose	r-value	-0.153	0.211	-0.292	-0.213	0.49	0.221	-0.312	0.019	
	p-value	0.694	0.585	0.446	0.583	0.18	0.569	0.414	0.962	

Note:

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.